

The Evolution of the Automotive Industry in Uzbekistan: Trends in Manufacturing Growth

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ABSTRACT:

The Uzbekistan's automotive industry is considered to be a crucial driver of economic value creation and employment generation across Central and North Asia, highlighting its significance on the global stage. Therefore, it is of importance to analyse this industry. The aim of this research is to discuss the historical development of the automotive industry in Uzbekistan, exploring its evolution from inception in 1992 through to 2019. The study provides a comprehensive overview of the current state of the industry, underscoring key milestones and trends. It examines the factors that have contributed to the industry's growth, including strategic partnerships with international automotive manufacturers from the Republic of South Korea, the Federal Republic of Germany and the United States of America, economic policies and government support which have intensively fueled its expansion.

Keywords: joint enterprise, mass production, Uzbek automotive industry, "UzDEUAuto", "Uzavtosanoat".

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INTRODUCTION

The modern automotive industry in many countries around the globe is the leading sector to support their economies. According to the International Organization of Motor Vehicle Manufacturers (OICA), the global production of motor vehicles amounted to 90.78 million units in 2015 [7]. The consulting company A.T. Kearney estimates the contribution of the automotive industry to the global gross domestic product (GDP) at roughly 3% by developing many other industries and stimulating the growth of employment not only in the production of automobiles but also in its maintenance, increasing trade turnover, strengthening the monetary system, determining the need for all industrial products. In the more advanced developing countries, the industry has actually proved to be one of the most dynamic exporters of «new» manufactured goods [5]. Take for example these five leading countries in the automotive industry, namely China with 27.17 million automobiles, the USA with 11.33 million, Japan with 9.58 million, Germany with 5.37 million and India with 5.17 million units in 2017. Developing countries also have a share and profit from the automotive industry [2]. Mexico, Turkey, Spain, Indonesia, the Philippines and Uzbekistan have adopted an industrialization strategy based on import substitution and have chosen the automotive industry as one of the main mechanisms for "launching the country's development process".

The Uzbek automotive industry is crucial in terms of surplus value and employment, not only in Uzbekistan but also in Central Asia. Especially, established in the first years of independence from the Soviet Union in 1991, it has become one of the foundations of industry and a driver of the country's technological development and modernization, initially focusing on assembling imported kits. In particular, the automotive industry has become a starting point for the development of such industries as chemical, oil, engineering, non-ferrous metallurgy, electricity, construction and

transport services in the country. Over the years, it has evolved into a dynamic and self-sustaining sector capable of producing a wide range of vehicles for both domestic and international markets. The automotive industry of Uzbekistan today is the modern production of cars and automotive components, with over 25,000 employees working in 100 large and medium enterprises of “Uzavtosanoat” JSC, the industry in collaboration with over 200 foreign companies [2]. Many global brands, including “Daewoo”, “General Motors”, “Volkswagen”, “Hyundai” and other car manufacturers are involved in the development of Uzbekistan’s automotive industry.

The growth rate of automotive sector serves as a key driver of economic progress, with Uzbekistan's automobile industry currently ranked 29th globally. At the moment, three head plants have been established in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan

- production of passenger cars under the American brand “Chevrolet”;
- medium-duty buses and trucks under the brand “Isuzu”;
- assembly of heavy-duty vehicles “MAN”;

Currently, the country produces 300,000 cars per year. As of January 2021, there were 2,955,295 vehicles registered in the country, with a motorization level of 80 vehicles per 1,000 inhabitants . Although the level of motorization in Uzbekistan is lower than in many developing countries (Brazil - 222 per 1,000 inhabitants, South Africa - 153 per 1,000 inhabitants), in the last ten years, the number of vehicles in Uzbekistan has doubled compared to the annual growth rate of 2-5% in Canada, the USA, Great Britain and Japan [1]. The car industry is the largest taxpayer in the country, contributing 6.6% to Uzbekistan's GDP and accounting for 11.7% of the industrial sector [4]. However, the industry was not always as we know it today, it took few decades to grow to its current size and achieve international recognition.

The aim of this research is to analyze and address the historical development of the automotive industry in Uzbekistan, highlight an overview of the situation, factors which influence the Uzbek automotive industry’s enhancement.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The development of the automotive industry in Uzbekistan goes back to the first years of reaching the independence of the country. Uzbek engineers in collaboration with international automotive manufacturers from the Republic of South Korea, the Federal Republic of Germany and the United States of America were working hand in hand to develop this industry on the land Uzbekistan. The following works and articles show us this progress.

In the work published by Z.T Gaibnazarova, history of the automotive industries and leading enterprise “UzDEUAuto” was analyzed [2]. According to the author, the history of enhancement is divided into four main stages where each stage is characterized by shift in management focus, priorities along with objectives. If in the beginning it is a focus on control, stability and training, over time, this focus was redirected to address an emphasis on motivation, dynamic innovations and global informatization.

In Sardor Tadjiev and Pierre-Yves Donze’s article, the primary focus is on how industrial policy has affected the growth of the automobile sector in five post-Soviet countries (Russia, Ukraine, Belarus, Uzbekistan, and Kazakhstan) since 1991 [8]. The authors point out that “UzDaewooAuto” benefited from customs duty exemptions provided by the free trade agreement among many former Soviet Union countries, which helped them grow their sales network and sell vehicles across the region. In the early 1990s, these countries had few protective barriers for their car markets, allowing UzDaewooAuto to quickly increase its sales.

METHODOLOGY

To achieve the aim of this work, thorough set of research methods are applied. These include an in-depth review and analysis of existing scientific literature and research articles related to the automotive industry in Uzbekistan, a synthesis of historical data and governmental policy reports

and, finally, a systematic approach is conducted to provide a broader context for understanding the industry's progression over time.

DISCUSSION

In the most general way the history of the industry and leading company "UzDEUAuto" (now "UzAuto Motors") can be divided into 4 main stages. The division into steps of development of the automotive industry in Uzbekistan in this case was based on the nature of the management tasks addressed at the stage under consideration.

First phase, 1992-1995 - The formation of enterprises, large-scale construction works, development of advanced foreign technologies for production of passenger cars. The main tasks were to form a team - selection, training and placement of employees, organization of cooperation with partners, preparation for production. Construction of facilities and infrastructure, installation, assembly and adjustment of production equipment were carried out.

Second stage, 1996-1999 - Start of production of cars on the "UzDEUAuto" joint venture, stabilization of product quality and production rate, development of a large-scale localization program. The issues of mastering technologies, starting production of commercial products, organization of car sales were addressed.

Third stage, 2000-2006 - The transition of the industry on the path of development, is characterized by qualitative growth of the industry. The development of the domestic automobile industry is characterized by the creation of a developed technological base and the development of new models. The "Matiz" model has been launched, innovation activities - rationalization and quality circles, management innovations and implementation of MBO (Management by Objectives) - were applied.

Fourth stage, 2007-2019 - Joining the world corporation, creation of "General Motors Uzbekistan" and "UzAuto Motors", rapid growth of capacity for production of components, model changes and opening of branches, including assembly plants abroad. Growth of production, creation of new manufacturing of parts, introduction of new control methods (GM-GMS - production according to GM global method). Each stage is characterized by a change in management focus and priorities, that is, the change of management objectives.

Historically, first, the automotive industry in Uzbekistan appeared in the early 90s. The first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Abduganiyevich Karimov during his official visit to the Republic of South Korea in June 1992 signed preliminary documents for the development of mutual economic cooperation between the two countries. In August of this year, in collaboration with the Republic of South Korea, it was agreed to establish a joint venture for automobile manufacturing in Uzbekistan [3].

On November 5, 1992, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan made a special decision on the establishment of the joint enterprise producing cars in cooperation with the "Selxozmash" concern and the "DEU kofogeuzpp" corporation. As part of this decision, the "Selxozmash" concern was tasked with developing a concept for the further advancement of the republic's automobile industry within three months [3]. On March 17, 1994, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan established a holding corporation called "Uzavtosanoat" to manage government shares in joint ventures and formulate policies for the growth of the automobile industry. As a result, the state-owned holding company's chairman and vice-chairman were also ministers and deputy ministers in the cabinet, respectively. In other words, "Uzavtosanoat" simultaneously took on role as both policymaker and a policy user [8].

In this way in 1992 in the Republic of Uzbekistan in partnership with "DEU" corporation of South Korea "UzDEUAuto" joint venture was established in Asaka with a total cost of 658 million US dollars. At that time, the assembly plant was equipped with the most modern technologies of Korea, qualified workers were accepted, including about 1000 young people from Uzbekistan who got their bachelor's degree in Korea. Mass production of the first model "Damas" minibuses at the Asaka Automobile Plant began in March 1996, and the official opening ceremony of the plant and international presentation were held on July 19, 1996, with the participation of the President of the Republic of

Uzbekistan Islam Karimov [3]. Starting from this point, the manufacture of “Nexia” and “Tico” models began. In 1996-1999, the joint enterprise "UzDEUAuto" produced more than 200,000 cars, and a total of about 60,000 by 1999 ("Nexia" - 28,259, "Tico" - 16,380, "Damas" - 13,663 units, licensed and slightly upgraded copies of Opel Kadett, Suzuki Alto and Suzuki Every) [6]. More than 14 thousand cars were exported abroad.

Taking advantage of customs duty exemptions under the free-trade agreement among many former Soviet Union countries, “UzDEUAuto” was able to expand its sales network and sell vehicles throughout much of the region. In the early 1990s, most of these countries had not yet established significant protective barriers for their automotive markets, allowing “UzDEUAuto” to experience rapid sales growth. As a result, exports grew from 900 units in 1996 to 109,000 in 2007, with domestic production reaching 168,600 units that year (Figure 1). Over 12 years, “UzDEUAuto” exported 361,000 vehicles, with the majority going to Russia (88%) and Ukraine (7%) [9]. The large production volumes enabled the company to invest in the localization of parts, contributing to the technological advancement of the industry.

Figure 1. Motor Vehicle (Passenger and Commercial) Sales, Exports, and Local Production in Uzbekistan for 196-2019

Note: Data available before 1996

Also, according to the contract signed between "Uzavtosanoat" association and Turkey's "Koch Holding" company in 1995, a joint venture "SamKochAvto" was launched the annual project capacity of which made up more than 5,000 buses and various trucks in the city of Samarkand with the total cost of 65 million US dollars [3].

On March 16, 1999, in Central Asia the official launch ceremony of this unique bus and truck manufacturing company was held. In this year 163 buses and 302 trucks were produced, whilst in 2000, these indicators constituted 483 and 102, respectively. Currently, 25% of the vehicle components and spare parts manufactured at "SamKochAvto" are produced in Uzbekistan. In the future, it is planned to increase this rate significantly. Being made mere 15% of the primary

components at the Asaka Automobile Plant in local enterprises, this trend reached 55% by 1999 [3]. In order to implement the program of localization of production of components for automobiles of the Republic of Uzbekistan, numerous joint ventures were established. The factories like "UzKoramKo", "Uz-Tong Hong", "Uz-Dong Yang", "Uz-Dongju Paint Company" and "Uz-Sam Yang" were established with the participation of South Korean partners. In 1998 the "Uzavtosanoat" association joined the International Organization of Automotive Manufacturers. On October 30, 2006, the joint venture was reorganized into "SamAvto" LLC, and the share of the Turkish party was bought by "Uzavtosanoat". The founders of the newly formed company included "Uzavtosanoat" and Isuzu that influenced on the product. In 2007 production of buses and trucks under the "Isuzu" brand began. It was announced that "UzOtoyol" cars, previously manufactured by "SamAvto" will receive service parts from Isuzu [10].

In 1999, the "UzDaewoo" car factory was awarded the ISO-9001 certificate, and in August 2001, a new, more modern line of the factory was put into operation, as a result of which the new "Matiz" car model began to be produced, that, in turn, in March 2003 was nominated as «Car of the Year» on the market of the Russian Federation. In August of the same year another new "Lacetti" model was launched. As time goes by, exact car models require some changes and enhancements in order to meet all needs and requirements which is what the company doing. In December 2004 "Matiz" started to be equipped with a 1.0 liter engine and automatic transmission and was renamed as "Matiz Best", while "Damas B150" entered production replacing "B100" in February 2006 [11].

In 2007, on the basis of "UzDaewooAuto" company, "GM-Uzbekistan" company was established in cooperation with "General Motors Corporation" and only on November 27, 2008, the production began. The first assembled car on this day was a "Chevrolet Lacetti" which was the millionth assembled vehicle out of the production from "UzAvtosanoat" [3]. Further more modern cars like "Captiva", "Epica", "Takuma" in 2007 and "Spark" in 2010 started to be manufactured under the "Chevrolet" brand. As part of a new agreement, in November 2011 the joint venture "GM Powertrain Uzbekistan" launched an engine plant in Tashkent, 400 kilometers from "GM Uzbekistan's" vehicle production facility in Asaka. "GM" holds a 52% stake, while "UzAvtosanoat" owns 48% of the "Powertrain" joint venture. This factory is GM's first engine plant in Uzbekistan and is set to produce over 225,000 Ecotec 1.2L and 1.5L engines annually for GM's small passenger cars worldwide [12]. This joint venture was granted the same privileges and government support as the previous one. In the period of time between 2011 and 2012, there were several changes in the model range of the company by introducing upgraded "Captiva" and a completely new model - "Malibu". In 2012, the "Cobalt" was added to the production line. In this way, a solid foundation of automobile industry was created [11].

In 2010, about 5,000 employees were employed at the "GM Uzbekistan" assembly plant. "GM Uzbekistan" sold 121,584 vehicles locally in 2011, making the country the eighth-largest market for Chevrolet. In January 2014 was held the opening ceremony of the new branch of "GM Uzbekistan" in Pitnak [12].

In this period there were conducted negotiations with the Federal Republic of Germany that led to launching completely new "JV Man Auto-Uzbekistan" joint venute in 2009. It was established according to the agreement between "Uzavtosanoat" and "MAN SE" companies and initially was signed by the first President of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov and by the Chief Executive Officer of "MAN SE" Hokan Samuelsson [3]. The factory is located in Samarkand. For the stable operation of the enterprise, all employees learned the German language and were trained by German specialists. At first, during 2009-2012, trucks were produced at the Samarkand Automobile Factory. Only in 2012, the "MAN" automobile plant was completed. One of the models currently assembled is the "MAN TGA", imported as a CKD kit from Germany. Another is the "MAN CLA", a nearly identical truck produced by the Indian manufacturer MAN Force Trucks Pvt. Ltd. These units are also delivered as a CKD kit. MAN plans to launch a specifically modified version of the Indian "CLA" model for the Central Asian market, under the name "MAN CLE". The primary target markets for the models manufactured in Uzbekistan are the domestic Uzbek market and the "CIS" states. In addition to the "TGA" and the "CLA" series there are also the "TGA" and "TGM" series, the obsolete models "MAN F2000", "MAN M2000" and "MAN F8" are available. According to the plan, the plant was meant to produce 500 to 1500 trucks per year and export to the Post-Soviet states [12]. The production capacity is expected to rise later to more than 2000 units.

“UzAvtosanoat” is the only truck manufacturer in Central Asia and aims to dominate the commercial vehicle sector. After the collapse of their former joint venture “SamKochAvto”, “MAN SE” has emerged as a promising new partner. However, in the late 2009, Hakan Samuelsson, a German representative of “MAN SE”, was involved in a bribery scandal [13]. There have been assumptions that “UzAvtosanoat” might be involved or affected by this scandal.

From 2008 and 2017, “GM Uzbekistan” expanded its capacity to 300,000 vehicles annually and arranged the manufacturing of six new models. Between 2008 and 2019, “Uzavtosanoat” invested in enhancing local suppliers' capacities, increased the localization of imported subcomponents, and established 12 new domestic companies for parts production, primarily through partnerships with South Korean firms [9]. However, the Russian economic crisis and declining oil prices in 2014 led to exchange rate instability and a significant reduction in consumer purchasing power in Uzbekistan and its export markets. Consequently, “GM Uzbekistan's” output volumes decreased from 235,100 units in 2014 to 84,800 units in 2016 (Figure 1) [3].

Currently, 10 models of cars under the brands “Chevrolet” and “Ravon”, in particular the models “Spark R2”, “Nexia R3”, “Cobalt R4”, “Lacetti (now Gentra)” are produced at three production sites of “UZAuto Motors”, mainly in Asaka, “Malibu”, “Tracker”, “Equinox”, “Trailblazer”, “Traverse” and “Tahoe” in the Tashkent branch, “Damas” models, “Labo” in the Pitnack branch. Suppliers “GM Uzbekistan” - more than 100, including sub-suppliers, main ones - «GM Powertrain Uzbekistan», «Uz SeMyung», «Uz Koram», «Uz Koje» «Avtokomponent», «Uz Dong Yang», «Uz Uz Dong Won Ko», «Uz Dong Ju Paint», «Uz Tong Hong Ko», «Uz Chasis», «Uz Sangwoo», «UzAuto-Aaustem», «Uz Minda», «Jizzax Akkumulyator Zavodi», «Uzeraealternator», «Uzerae Climate Control», «Uzeraeacable», «Uz Hanwoo Engineering», «Kwangin Autosystems», «Avtooyna» and others. At the moment, more than 3 million vehicles are registered in Uzbekistan, of which 89% are passenger cars. The domestic car market is estimated at \$2.6 billion US dollars - about 5% of Uzbekistan's GDP. Despite the significant growth in amount of produced cars during last 5-10 years, the number of passenger cars per capita still remains quite low - 90 per 1000 people. For comparison, this figure in Kazakhstan accounts for 202 pieces, in Russia - 300 pieces, in Germany - 567 pieces and 800 pieces in the USA. Thus, the car market of Uzbekistan has a great growth potential, though it is constrained by the population's purchasing power. The country's automotive industry has a strong promise of rapid growth and development.

CONCLUSION

The development of the automotive industry in Uzbekistan plays an essential role in generating surplus value and employment, not only within the country but also across Central Asia. The industry did not reach its current scale and international recognition overnight, it has undergone significant growth over the past few decades. Since its emergence in the 1990s, the sector has grown rapidly, thanks in large part to substantial government support. Uzbekistan now ranks 29th globally in the automotive industry, underscoring its significance on the world stage. The formation of a cluster around the Asaka automobile plant, composed of independent medium and small enterprises providing essential components and services, further highlights the industry's potential for sustainable growth and competitiveness.

It is essential to underline that there are very optimistic prognoses concerning the future position of the Uzbek automotive industry. The focus on innovation, sustainable development, and international cooperation is putting industry in a bright and prosperous future.

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